

Assessment of Knowledge, Attitude Regarding Generic Drugs among II MBBS Students, Kurnool Medical College, Kurnool: A Cross Sectional Study

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Abstract:

Background: WHO defines a generic product as “a pharmaceutical product, usually intended to be interchangeable with an innovator product, that is manufactured without a license from the innovator company and marketed after the expiry date of the patent or other exclusive rights. Lack of awareness or knowledge is another reason for doctors to provide branded medicines to get a patient’s trust.

Aim: The aim of the study was to evaluate knowledge and attitude toward generic medicines among resident and intern doctors at tertiary care teaching hospital.

Materials and Methods: The present study was carried out with 2nd MBBS students (200) in the department of pharmacology, at Kurnool medical college, Kurnool in the year 2023.

Result: In order to create awareness, the study was conducted on generic drugs, in II MBBS students. A total of 200 participants were included in study. A questionnaire on Knowledge and Attitude about generic drugs was circulated and awareness on generic drugs was assessed through responses obtained. 94.15% students were aware on BA/BE studies for generic drugs, 60.98% were aware of PMBJP Scheme. 71.22 % ,85.85%students expressed that generic drugs are as safe as branded drugs, and cost effective respectively. 71.71 % opined that they are not inferior to branded drugs.

Conclusion: In tertiary care teaching hospitals, there should be seminars or training programs to advance the use of generic medications and to increase understanding about them.

Keywords: PMBJP- Pradhan Mantri Bharatiya Janaushadhi Pariyojana, BA- bioavailability, BE- bioequivalent.

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Introduction

A generic product is defined as “a pharmaceutical product, usually intended to be interchangeable with an innovator product, that is manufactured without a license from the innovator company and marketed after the expiry date of the patent or other exclusive rights [1].

The pharmaceutical sector in India was predominantly dominated by foreign corporations in 1947, when the country gained its independence. Companies based in the US and Europe had almost 90% of the market [2]. In the early 1960s, the Indian government started encouraging the growth of domestic companies in the pharma sector. However,

it was not until 1970 that the aim was achieved [2,3,4,5]

In October 2016, the Medical Council of India amended the code of conduct for physicians and urged that all doctors prescribe medications with readable generic names and make sure the prescription is logical and encourages the use of generic medications.[6]

Keeping in view of Generic medicines, to create awareness, among the students, the present study was carried out

Materials and Methods

The present study was carried out with 2nd MBBS students (200) in the department of pharmacology, at Kurnool medical college, Kurnool in the year 2023.

Inclusion criteria:

Questionnaire regarding generic medicines is given to all 2nd MBBS students

(total 200 students) as a part of CBME curriculum and NMC schedule for II MBBS students.

Exclusion criteria :(44 students)

1. Who are not interested to participate in the study.

Statistical Analysis: Collected answers was entered in MS office Excel 2023 and analysis is done by SPSS version of software is 23.

Scale of analysis: through the responses obtained to the questionnaire.

Results:

Table 1: Knowledge among participants

Knowledge	Yes(%)	No(%)
After the Expiry of PATENT period of innovator drug the Generic medicines were marked	82(40)	123(60)
Preclinical research and clinical trials for generic medications need to be repeated by the generic drug manufacturer.	154(75.12)	51(24.88)
It is necessary for generic drug manufacturers to carry out bioavailability and bioequivalence studies in order to prove that their generic and innovator (patent) drugs are equivalent.	193(94.15)	12(5.85)
In India, a legislation mandates that doctors should, whenever feasible, give medications with generic names.	128(62.44)	77(37.56)
Aware of “Pradhan Mantri Bharatiya Janaushadhi Pariyojana”	125(60.98)	80(39.02)

Figure 1: Distribution of Knowledge among study participants

Table 2: Attitude

Attitude	Number	Percentage
Generic drugs are as safe as branded drugs (YES)	146	71.22
Generic drugs are inferior in efficacy to branded drugs (NO)	147	71.71
Generic medicines are cheaper than branded Medicine (YES)	176	85.85
A patient using branded drugs for his disease would accept generic medicines if prescribed (NO)	126	61.46
Training program for internees regarding of generic drugs prescription		
Strongly Agree	87	42.44
Agree	110	53.66
Pharmacist is legally empowered to purchase or sell generic drugs in place of prescribed innovator (patent) drug		
Strongly Agree	30	14.63
Agree	104	50.73
Awareness program for general public regarding generic drugs		
Strongly Agree	116	56.59
Agree	79	38.54
Generic drug pharmacy should be present in every hospital		
Strongly Agree	69	33.66
Agree	109	53.17

Figure 2: Distribution of Attitude

1. Training program for internees regarding of generic drugs prescription.
2. Pharmacist is legally empowered to purchase or sell generic drugs in place of prescribed innovator (patent) drug.
3. Awareness program for general public regarding generic drugs.
4. Generic drug pharmacy should be present in every hospital.

Table 3: Distribution of Practices among study participants

Practice	Yes(%)	No(%)
1. Prescribed generic medicines by any physician	121(59.03)	84(40.97)
2. Prefer to prescribe generic medicines for your patients, Once you start practicing	141(68.78)	64(31.22)

Discussion

Total of 200 participants are included in study (students of II MBBS, Kurnool Medical College, Kurnool).

Just 40% of students are aware that innovator pharmaceuticals lose their patent and are then replaced by generic versions. The incorrect belief held by 75.12% of students is that preclinical research should be repeated by generic medicine manufacturers. 94.15% students have opinion that for generic medicines need to undergo bioequivalence studies for ensuring quality assurance among doctors and patients. 62% students are aware that law governs that every physician should prescribe the generic drugs. 60.98% students aware that they are available at local pharmacy store (Pradhan Mantri Bharatiya Jana aushadhi Pariyojana Scheme).[1]

85% of students believe that patients' medical expenses can be decreased by using generic medications. 71.22% knew that name-brand and generic medications are equally safe. According to

the opinions of 61.46 percent of students, patients will not accept switching from branded to generic medications for their illness. According to 29% of respondents, branded medications are more effective than generic ones.

96% agree that there should be training programme for internees regarding generic drugs prescription. 65% of students agree that pharmacist is legally empowered to sell the generic drugs in place of innovator drug. 95% agree that there should be awareness programme on generic medicines in general public. 88% of students agree that generic drugs pharmacy should be attached to every government hospital.

59% students put forward that they have been prescribed generic drugs by physicians during the course of their illness. 68% of students prefer to start prescribing generic medicines to their patients once they start practice. It shows good knowledge and attitude towards generic drugs prescription among students.

The Indian pharmaceutical industry is the largest producer, manufacturer, and exporter of generic drugs in the world, accounting to 13 per cent of the global pharma market, as per recent report by Asian Lite.

The New Guidelines About?

According to the Indian Medical Council's (Professional Conduct, Etiquette and Ethics) Regulations, all registered medical practitioners are required to prescribe medications with clearly printed generic names.[7]

Exemption for prescribing generic drugs include

- 1) Medication with a narrow therapeutic index is one in which even a slight dosage variation may have unfavourable effects.
- 2) Biosimilar -A different version of biologic products that are manufactured in living systems and Similar other exceptional cases.

Steps taken to promote generic drugs?

The World Health Organization's Good Manufacturing Practices (WHO-GMP) certified suppliers are the only ones from whom the Pharmaceuticals and Medical Devices Bureau of India purchases medications. [1]

National Accreditation Board for Testing and Calibration Laboratories (NABL)-accredited labs test each medicine batch. The medications are only sent to PMBJP Kendras after passing quality testing. The National Health Mission (NHM) oversees the implementation of the free medicines policy. Its goal is to give public health facilities free access to necessary generic medications. [1]

According to the 2002 Indian Medical Council (Professional Conduct, Etiquette and Ethics) Regulations, all doctors must prescribe medications

Pradhan Mantri Bhartiya Janaushadhi Pariyojana (PMBJP) [9,10]

More than 9600 Pradhan Mantri Bhartiya Janaushadhi Kendras (PMBJK), administered by the Ministry of Chemicals and Fertilizers, have been built up spanning all districts of the country in order to promote generic medications with quality and at reasonable costs to everyone.

The Pharmaceutical Medicines Bureau of India (PMBI) also manages the Janaushadhi Sugam mobile application, which is a single-window platform that helps users find local PMBJKs, look up Janaushadhi medications, find phone numbers, etc. In addition, Janaushadhi Diwas is observed annually on March 7 in order to raise awareness of Scheme [9]

with generic names that are clearly readable, ideally in capital letters. [1,2]

According to clause 1.5 of the Indian Medical Council (Professional Conduct, Etiquette and Ethics) Regulations, 2002, doctors must make sure that prescriptions are prescribed and used rationally, and they must prescribe medications with generic names that are legible, preferably in capital letters.

Furthermore, all Registered Medical Practitioners have been instructed to abide by the aforementioned regulations by Circulars dated 22.11.2012, 18.01.2013, and 21.04.2017, which were issued by the former Medical Council of India (MCI). [9,10]

The National Medical Commission Act, 2019 gives the Ethics and Medical Registration Board (EMRB)

of the National Medical Commission or the relevant State Medical Councils the authority to discipline a physician who violates a regulation.[10]

Additionally, IMA has requested that the Center implement a "one drug, one quality, one price" system in which only generic medications are permitted while guaranteeing the highest possible quality of these medications, and all brands must be offered at the same price and either controlled or outlawed. [8]

Bioequivalent studies to be displayed in the clinics, hospitals so that it creates and establishes trust in all health professional as well as public [9,10]. All generic drugs to be available in all pharmacies, as some pharmacies are deficient in generic drugs including emergency generic drugs also. Physicians are to be counselled for creating sensitisation in the patients in promotional prescription. All patients irrespective of their financial background are to be prescribed generic medicines. In corporate hospitals generic drug prescriptions to be implemented actively.

Conclusion:

The majority of doctors were found to have positive attitudes and good understanding on the use of generic medications. It was discovered that a sizable portion of respondents lacked technical and regulatory understanding of the pharmacokinetic and bioequivalency characteristics of generic medications. In tertiary care teaching hospitals, there should be seminars or training programs to advance the use of generic medications and to increase understanding about them.

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